

Increase and transfer knowledge to producers about precision fertigation of Cork Oak (*Quercus suber* L.) in intensive cork production stands.

Introduction

The production of cork in the last decades have been decreasing in quantity and quality, because of bad management practices, biotic factors (pests and diseases), and harsher weather conditions (less precipitation and higher temperatures).

This project had as an objective the study of fertigation in cork oak stands, to increase the profit of the stakeholders and create a simple guide for the landowners to be able to follow. A few landowners, by their own initiative experimented watering some cork oak trees in their lands, which started this experiment. After they have seen some progress, they contacted diverse institutions to share the results and to create a proper trial to evaluate the growth differences. The results were gathered in chapters available online and printed in "Cork Oak with fertigation: Support handbook for the first years." ("Sobreiros com fertirrega: Manual de apoio aos primeiros anos"), "Young stands - Case study REGASUBER" ("Povoamentos jovens - Caso de estudo REGASUBER"), Young stands in pre-first debarking - Case study IRRICORK" ("Povoamentos jovens em situação de pré-desbóia - Caso de estudo IRRICORK"), and "Old stands" ("Povoamentos Adultos").

This chapters were freely distributed to forest owners associations and diverse entities related forestry, which allows the information to reach the landowner."

Lessons learned

This project was a case of success because it allowed the forest owners to have their own initiative and be rewarded for such behaviour. It was a rich experiment in terms of knowledge share because different kind companies, institutions and landowners were involved in this project.

The connections and communication between the different concerned parties was one of the key factors for this project success.

All the results of the different case studies allowed the creation of different scientific articles, in this way sharing the results with the academic and scientific community. And the creations of handbooks, easily

available to the landowners, which allow them to recreate the experiments and see for themselves the results in different stand and site conditions. "

Figure 1. The printed chapters related to the project.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.goregacork.uevora.pt/>

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union (Grant n. 101086216). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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